

DMLEX on Wikibase: Legacy dictionaries as collaboratively editable dataset

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Overview

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- Part 1: From source to DMLex
 - Source data, legacy XML
 - Conversion to DMLex
 - LLM-augmented workflows
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 - Remodeling DMLex sources
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Data Model for Lexicography Approved as an OASIS Standard

29 May 2025

<https://www.oasis-open.org/2025/05/29/dmlex-approved-as-oasis-standard/>

More about Wikibase in DH: <https://dhwiki.wikibase.cloud>

Introduction

- **Context:** Lexicography has shifted from printed pages to interconnected digital ecosystems (Linked Data).
- **Objective:** Convert legacy digitized dictionaries into the DMLEX standard.
- **Goal:** Import standardized data into a Wikibase instance for collaborative editing.
- **Pipeline:**
 - Legacy XML → DMLex
 - DMLex → Wikibase

Part 1: Legacy XML to DMLex

Source Data

- **Origin:** 6 legacy bilingual dictionaries from the RSDO infrastructure project.
- **License:** Open source (CC-BY-SA 4.0).
- **Format History:**
 - Originally compiled for print.
 - Laid out with desktop-publishing software.
 - Exported to a bespoke, project-specific XML schema.
- **Examples:** Slovenian-SerboCroatian, Slovenian-English, English-Slovenian, Slovenian-German.

Why DMLex?

- **Standard:** Developed by lexicographers for lexicographers.
- **Nature:** Serialization-independent model (XML, JSON, RDF).
- **Purpose:** Universal and modular representation of lexicographic data.
- **Benefit:** Provides a standardized pivot format before importing into Wikibase, ensuring data is tool-agnostic and future-proof.

Data Model for Lexicography (DMLex) Version 1.0

OASIS Standard

29 April 2025

<https://docs.oasis-open.org/lexidma/dmllex/v1.0/dmllex-v1.0.html>

Legacy XML to DMLex Transformation

Strategy: Three parallel tracks to handle data heterogeneity.

- **Custom Scripts:**

- Used for tags with clear one-to-one mappings to DMLex.

- **Manual Refinement:**

- Skilled lexicographers carrying out quick, low-effort edits.

- **LLM-Augmented Workflows:**

- Using Large Language Models (GPT-4) for complex tasks where manual work would be too heavy.

Transformation: Straightforward Mappings

- Lookup tables defined 1:1 correspondences between old tags and DMLex equivalents.
- Automated via script.
- **Example:** *sam.* in legacy converted to *noun* in DMLex

Transformation: Splitting & Expansion

- **List Splitting:**

- Legacy: križarski, krstaški (Comma-separated).
- DMLex: Split into individual objects.

- **Tilde Expansion:**

- Legacy: Uses tildes (~) or dashes to save space (e.g., anglikanski... ~a cerkev).
- Action: Resolve placeholders to full forms (anglikanska cerkev).

- **Suffix Expansion:**

- Legacy: -čki (implied stem).
- Action: Combine stem + ending to create full forms.

Transformation: Data structure issues

- **Challenge:** Legacy content often places metadata (domain, style, grammar) immediately before specific translations.
- **DMLex Constraint:** Metadata is typically attached to the *Sense*, not directly to a translation string.

```
<GN>agregat</GN>
<S>
<TR1/><KP>tehn.</KP> <IN>za proizvodjanje moči</IN> <TR>engine</TR>
<TR1/><KP2>tehn.</KP2> <KO>pogonski, hladilni</KO> <TR>unit</TR>
<TR1/><KP2>tehn.</KP2> <IN>za proizvodjanje elektrike</IN> <KO>električni</KO> <TR>generator</TR>
</S>
<S>
<TR1/><KP>ekon.</KP> <TR>aggregate</TR>
<FR><FRB>denarni agregat</FRB> <FRP>monetary aggregate</FRP></FR>
</S>
```

Transformation: Data structure issues

- **Solution:**

- Split the original "sense" into multiple, more granular senses.
- Ensure each translation with specific metadata gets its own Sense container.
- Prioritized data fidelity over adherence to the original print macrostructure.

```
<GN>agregat</GN>
<S>
<TR1/><KP>tehn.</KP> <IN>za proizvodvanje moči</IN> <TR>engine</TR>
<TR1/><KP2>tehn.</KP2> <KO>pogonski, hladilni</KO> <TR>unit</TR>
<TR1/><KP2>tehn.</KP2> <IN>za proizvodvanje elektrike</IN> <KO>električni</KO> <TR>generator</TR>
</S>
<S>
<TR1/><KP>ekon.</KP> <TR>aggregate</TR>
<FR><FRB>denarni agregat</FRB> <FRP>monetary aggregate</FRP></FR>
</S>
```

LLM-Augmented Workflows

- **Role:** Delegated specific tasks where rule-based scripts failed and manual work was inefficient.
- **Model:** OpenAI GPT-4o.
- **Method:** In-context learning (Few-shot prompting).
- **Primary Use Case:** Phrase expansion and correction (e.g., resolving incomplete examples or matching translations).
- **Validation:** Output assessed by expert review rather than automated benchmarks.

LLM Prompting Strategy

- **System Role:** "You are a lexicographer specialized in Slovenian dictionaries."
- **Instructions:** detailed logic for handling specific edge cases (e.g., "If headword starts with a dash...").
- **Demonstration:** Provided several diverse examples in the prompt to guide the model.
- **Output Format:** JSON or raw text for easy integration into the pipeline.

LLM Task Examples

Example 1: Phrase Expansion

Input:

Headword: *abeceda*

Phrase: *klicati po -i*

LLM Output:

klicati po abecedi

```
<G>abeceda</G> <BV>imenica</BV> <FRB>klicati po -i</FRB>
```

```
<!-- correct output -->
```

```
klicati po abecedi
```

Example 2: Translation Expansion

Input:

Headword: bazalni

SL Example: membrana

DE Example: Basalmembran

LLM Output:

bazalna membrana

```
<!-- legacy -->
<NUM>002720</NUM><FRB>bazalni</FRB>
<SL>membrana</SL><DE2>Basalmembran</DE2>

<!-- correct output -->
bazalna membrana

<!-- legacy -->
<NUM>003582</NUM><FRB>zdravilno blato</FRB>
<SL>obloga z zdravilnim blatom</SL><DE2>Fangopackung</DE2>

<!-- correct output -->
obloga z zdravilnim blatom
```

Part 2: DMLex to Wikibase

What is Wikibase?

- A set of extensions to MediaWiki
- Used, first and foremost, by Wikidata (since 2012)
- Since 2018: Wikibase for everybody
 - Wikibase Suite (for self-hosting)
 - Wikibase Cloud (free WMDE hosting service)
- Wikibase, a Linked Data editing and publishing platform
 - Describes entities and their relations (Knowledge Graph)
 - Items (Q), Lexemes (L), Properties (P), EntitySchemes (E), Media files (M)
- Outstanding features
 - Every entity has a (editable) page
 - Collaborative editing, reversible entity edit and user contribution histories
 - Text pages, Query service, SPARQL endpoint, mediaWiki API

What are Wikibase ‘lexemes’?

- L-entities or ‘**lexemes**’ describe single-word or multiword lexical items
- Underlying data model: [Ontolex-Lemon](#)
 - **Entry – Sense – Form**
 - **All three have unique and global URI**
- Example
 - **Entry** <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/L3549>, ‘foot’ (noun, English)
 - **Sense** L35491-S1, ‘customary unit of length’, item for this sense Q3710
 - **Sense** L35491-S2, ‘furniture part’, item for this sense Q5465724
 - **Sense** L35491-S3, ‘anatomical structure found in vertebrates’, item for this sense Q15807
 - **Form** L3549-F1, ‘foot’, singular
 - **Form** L3549-F2, ‘feet’, plural

See [Lindemann 2025](#)

Wikibase Ontology: Lexemes

- Ontolex-Lemon core classes
 - Lexical Entry
 - Lexical Sense
 - Form
- Some default properties
 - have to be used, no alternative
 - appear as such in RDF representation
- Everything else is up to the user
 - ...and always modeled as **statement**

ontolex:LexicalEntry

wikibase:lemma

wikibase:lexicalCategory

dct:language

ontolex:sense

ontolex:lexicalForm

ontolex:LexicalSense

skos:definition

ontolex:Form

wikibase:grammaticalFeature

ontolex:representation

Wikibase Lexeme

- Lexical Entry
 - 1 Lemma per language code
 - 1 lexical category, 1 language
 - n statements
- Form
 - 1 representation per lang code
 - n grammatical features
 - n statements
- Sense
 - 1 gloss per lang code
 - n statements

Wikibase Statements

- A **statement** consists of
 - 1 **claim** (a semantic triple)
 - 1 statement blank node
 - n **qualifier** triples
 - n reference blank nodes
 - n **reference** triples
 - a **rank** value (1 out of 3)
- Same property number in different namespaces
 - .../prop/direct/P123
 - .../prop/P123
 - .../prop/statement/P123

Remodeling of DMLex sources

- In general, straightforward
 - same core elements entry, sense, form, in the same hierarchical order
 - exception: dmlex:Sense to ontolex:Sense (and not ontolex:LexicalConcept)
- Fit DMLex elements to Wikibase statement format
 - in practice, straightforward in most cases (in theory, illegal)

Translation equivalents

Lexeme Discussion

(L111487) **korpus**
sl

Language Slovene
Lexical category samostalnik

[see in Wikibase](#)

Statements

instance of	dmlex Entry	
	dmlex source ID	SLEN-P_008394_korpus_1
		→ 0 references

- In DMLex they can have forms
 - This does not fit in a *statement*
- We model them as Lexical Entry
- They obtain own URI and own page

```
<headwordTranslation>  
<text>korpus</text>  
<inflectedForm>  
  <text>corpora</text>  
  <label tag="množina" />  
</inflectedForm>  
</headwordTranslation>
```

Lexeme Discussion

(L111490) **corpus**
en

Language English
Lexical category samostalnik

[see in Wikibase](#)

Statements

instance of	dmlex headword translation object	
		→ 0 references
dmlex source dictionary	Priročni slovensko-angleški slovar (v. 3.2)	
		→ 0 references

Senses

L111490-S1 | Slovenian | korpus

Statements about L111490-S1

translation source sense	korpus (corpus)	
		0 references

Forms

L111490-F1 | corpora
en

Grammatical features

Statements about L111490-F1

dmlex Label	množina	
		0 references

Examples

- In DMLex, inside <sense>
 - Forces to create “dummy sense objects” for examples that cannot be associated to a described sense (senseless examples)
 - Examples to appear outside senses is normal (“unintegrated microstructure”, [Prinsloo & Gouws](#) following Wiegand)
- In Wikibase, as child of <entry>
 - If the subject sense is known, it is linked in a qualifier
 - If the subject form is known, it is linked in a qualifier
 - Can link examples to more than one sense or form
 - Can list sense or form-less examples: they wait for being associated to a sense and a form

dmlex example		to become ineffective (English)
see in Wikibase		subject sense L467554-S1
		dmlex example translation prenehati veljati (Slovenian)

[see an example on Wikidata](#)

DMLex issues to review

- Examples forced to be child of sense
 - In the source datasets: examples on entry level (in DMLex XML, “dummy sense” objects)
 - It is normal not to be (immediately) able to associate an example to a sense (if finding in a corpus)!
 - In dictionaries, it is normal to find examples without explicit association to a sense
- Example types / *Collocation* (or *phrase*) as item type of its own?
 - DMLex: “Represents a sentence or other text fragment which illustrates the headword being used.”
 - It seems necessary to be able to annotate examples with example types
 - [Prinsloo/Gouws](#): Example types do not include *collocations* or *phrasemes*
 - [Wiegand](#): “nicht satzwertige Syntagmen (Kollokationsangaben, Phrasemangaben)” vs., in examples, “satzwertige Syntagmen” (complete sentences)
- Underspecification of language in string values
 - (A) Language of the lemma list and (B) language of the translation equivalents
 - No separation of object language(s) and metalanguage
 - Strings inherit their language from A or B

<https://lexbib.elex.is/wiki/Lexeme:L491832#S1>

dmlex definition	puška (English)
	dmlex definition type indicator

Controlled Values

```
<labelTag tag="astronomija" typeTag="domain" />
```

[see in Wikibase](#)

- DMLex controlled values module allows to prepare label linking
 - Represent label values as items, and link them to ontological entities

Results

- Script for DMLex transformation and upload to Wikibase
 - python, using [wikibaseintegrator](#)
 - A copy of the script at https://lexbib.elex.is/wiki/DMLEX_XML_upload_script
- Several large dictionaries on Wikibase, 900k lexical entries
 - Go to https://lexbib.elex.is/wiki/DMLEX_on_Wikibase
 - Ready for further enrichment, also through collaborative editing
 - Link entries describing the same lemma to each other, link senses, etc.
 - Harmonize controlled vocabularies for labels, etc., through entity linking
- DMLex on Wikibase is possible
 - We have encountered some issues
- Wikibase Cloud, current limitations
 - Large datasets and upload rate limits, query timeouts
 - For follow-up experiments and larger projects: IJS now self-hosting Wikibase

Conclusions and Outlook

In future larger projects...

- We will use DMLex
 - 3 different serializations
 - generic enough for multiple use cases
 - confronting the model with real-world dictionary content will improve it further
- We will use Wikibase
 - every lexical entry has its HTML page
 - content is queryable using SPARQL
 - content is collaboratively editable
- We will give recommendations for adapting DMLex better to the Wikibase data model

Questions?

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